

A REVIEW ON NITYA SHEELANIYA AHAR DRAVYA W.S.R. TO GOGHRITA**Ketakee K. Bharad*¹, Harish Kumar Purohit², Brijesh R. Mishra³**¹Post Graduate Scholar, Department of PG Ayurved Samhita and Siddhant, Shri Ayurved Mahavidyalaya, Nagpur, Maharashtra, India.²Associate Professor, Department of PG Ayurved Samhita and Siddhant, Shri Ayurved Mahavidyalaya, Nagpur, Maharashtra, India.³Professor, HOD and Principal Department of PG Ayurved Samhita and Siddhant, Shri Ayurved Mahavidyalaya, Nagpur, Maharashtra.***Corresponding Author: Ketakee K. Bharad**

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ABSTRACT

Ayurveda is one of the Ancient system of medicine. Ayurveda *Acharya's* taught us about health, how to living healthy life in society through Ahara Niyama by following Pathyapathya. Which Ahara can be taken in all season, which one is good for specific session. In classics there is in detail Description regarding the concepts like *Dincharya, Ritucharya, Sadvritta palan, Nitya Asheelniya Ahara Dravya, Nitya Sheelniya Ahara Dravya, etc.* Ahara (food) has been recognized as an important Pillar for human being. Ayurveda enhance the importance of Wholesome Ahara Dravya in Maintenance of health as well as prevention of diseases. As per Ayurveda, *Nitya Sheelaniya Ahara Dravya(Nitya Prayunjeeta Ahara) Dravya's are those food articles which are suitable for regular use e.g. Ghrith, Mudga, Saidhav, Amalak, Yava, Madhu, Saidhav, Shashtikshali, etc.* These food items with regular consumption can lead to overall health of person and also prevent from getting diseases. Ghrith is one of the most popular traditional dairy product in India. Ayurveda Classics describes the Eight different types of Ghrith/Ghee which are obtained from milk of eight different animals. Among all Ghrith obtained from milk of cow (Go Ghrith/Goghee) is considered the best. *Go Ghrith* has been used for Centuries to improve Physical and Mental health and also in treatment of various ailments.

KEYWORDS: Sheelaniya Dravya, Ahara, Ghrita, Goghrit.**INTRODUCTION**

Nitya Sheelaniya Ahara Dravya means the food items which should be used on daily basis for leading healthy life. According to the ayurveda, *Nitya Sheelaniya Ahara Dravya* are enlisted in *Charak Samhita, Ashtang Hridaya* and *Ashtang Sangraha*.

According to the Dictionary of Monier William's the word Nitya mean 'for long time', *Sheelaniya* means 'one should be habitual to take'. "*Abhyaset -Nirantarum Upayunjeet*" "(should be used regularly). *Acharya's* explained the importance of *Sheelniya ahara* by stating that if a person intake wholesome means *Sheelaniya Ahara* then there is no need of medicine and if a person consumes *Asheelaniya*(unwholesome) Ahara Dravya it manifest diseases.

The sheelaniya ahara dravya mentioned in *Charak* are *Mudag, Shashtikshali, Saidhav, Madhu, Amalak, Antreeksha payl, Sarpi, (ghrit) Jangalam.*^[1] Ghrith is one of them, which is foremost substance of Indian Cuisine from centuries. Since vedic era, it has been used for religious rites, cooking, cosmetic and medicinal purposes. Ayurveda describes 8 different types of Ghrita which are obtained from 8 different animal such as Cow, Buffelow, Goat, Camel Sheep, Elephant, Human, Single Hoofed animals. Among all, Ghrith obtained from cow milk is considered the best.^[2] *Goghrita* (cow ghee), is called as *Amritopam* (the elixir of life). It performs a lot of actions by virtue of its enormous properties.

Ghee word is originated from Sanskrit word 'Ghrith.' It is known as Neyi, Nai (south india), Roghan (Persian) and clarified butter, Butterfat, Dehydrated butter (English).

In ayurveda Goghrita is either used as single drug or as blinder or vehicle for other drugs.

Since, it is rich in lipids easily crosses Blood Brain Barrier and used extensively in treatment of Psychosomatic disorders along with other drugs as Ghrit Kalpana (Medicated Ghee). It is considered as best *Yogavahi* Dravya which potentiates the actions of other medicines without changing its own properties.

In Ayurveda and ancient Scriptures if not specified, the word Ghrita always applies to Goghrita.

Nirukti

The word Ghrita is derived from “*Ghriti Ghriyate Ghri Seke Anjighrisibhyah Ktah*”^[3]

Ghrita Nishpatt

Ghrita (cow ghee) is used in the meaning of ‘extracted from milk.’

MATERIAL AND METHODS

Review of literature was done with the help of ancient and present scriptures of Ayurveda, research articles.

DISCUSSION

Goghrita In Samhita

1. Charaka Samhita

(1000 B.C.-400 A.D.) Goghrita is beneficial for providing nutrition to all the dhatu and ojas of body. It is considered as best among all types of ghrita. It is best in alleviating vatapitta dushti. It is having Chakshusya, Balya, Vrīsyā, Kanthya, Jeevaneeya, Medhya, Vishaghna, Kaphakara and Vatapittaharaproperties. It is indicated in Jeerna jvara, Kshaya, Visha, Daha, Shotha, Shoola, Unmada, Apasmara, Mada, Murcchaand many other diseases. It pacifies vata by snehana karma, pitta by sheeta veerya and kapha dosha by samskara with other drugs. It specially pacifies pitta by the virtue of its madhura rasa and vipaka, sheeta veerya and manda guna.^[4]

2. Sushruta Samhita

(1000 B.C.-500 A.D.) Goghrita is chakshusya, balya, vatapitta doshahara having Madhura vipaka and sheeta veerya.^[5]

3. Astanga Hridayam

(600 A.D.) It is snehottam and best among vayasthapana (anti-ageing) drugs having sahasraveerya doing sahasra karma, which indicates the high potency and greater utility of ghrita.^[6]

B. Goghrita In Nighantu

1. Dhanvantari Nighantu

(10th-13th Century A.D.) In this nighntu, Goghritais described in Suvarnadi varga considered as best in chakshusya and balya karma.^[7]

2. Madanapala Nighantu

(1374 A.D.) Madanapala describes Goghrita in Paneeyadi varga. The properties and actions of ksheeroththa ghrita, purana ghrita and kumbh Sarpi is also given here.^[8]

3. Kaiyadev Nighantu

(1425 A.D.) In this nighntu, the properties and action of ghrita in general and goghrita in particular are given in Drava varga-Ghrita varga similar to previous description.^[9]

4. Bhavaprakasha Nighantu

(16th Century A.D.) Bhavmishra especially describes the properties and action of Gavya ghrita (cow ghee) in Ghrita varga. He calls it rasayana (rejuvenator) and better than all other sources of ghrita.^[10]

Pharmacodynamics^[11]

- 1] Gana-Madhura skandha
- 2] Source-Jagama sneha
- 3] Latin Name: Butyrum depuratum L.
- 4] Synonyms: Ajya, Havishya, Sarpi
- 5] Rasa: Madhura
- 6] Guna Guru, Snigdha, Mridu
- 7] Veerya : Sheeta
- 8] Vipaka : Madhura
- 9] Prabhava: Medhya, Vishaghna
- 10] Doshaprabhava : Vata-pittashamaka
- 11] Actions-Deepaniya, Snehana, Anulomana, Hridya, Vrīshya, Garbhasthapana, Jvaraghna, Dahaprashamana, Balya, Brihmana, Rasayana, Chakshusya, Yogavahi.

Therapeutic Uses-Raktapitta, Parshvashoola, Karshya, Daurbalya, Udavarta, Gulma, Kasa, Garbhapata, Jeerna jvara, Timira, Unmada, Apsmara.

Functions of Goghrita according to different Acharaya's

Sr.No.	Functions	Ch.	Su.	A.S	A.H.
1	Vatahara	+	+	+	+
2	Pittahara	+	+	+	+
3	Vrīshya	-	+	-	-
4	Ojovardhaka	+	+	-	-
5	Medhya	+	+	+	+
6	Balakara	+	+	+	+
7	Swaraprasadana	+	+	+	+
8	Varnaprasadana	+	-	-	-
9	Vayasthapana	-	+	+	+

CONCLUSION

It may be concluded that use of Go ghrita in our routine daily life, as gives good result and delays the ageing procedure by keeping us healthy and fit forever. Goghrita is one of the best sneha among four and best among all the eight types of Ghrita described in Ayurveda from different animals. Ghrita has one property Samskarasyanuvartanum i.e. there is no other such material which imbibes the quality to the extent that Ghrita does Use of Go ghrita is best described in Ayurveda. Ayurved have described its use in the

treatment part as well as in diet and as immunomodulator.

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